

DIFFICULTIES OF LEARNING ARABIC

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Annotation: Learning Arabic requires commitment and determination. Learning Arabic can be difficult, but don't forget that every new thing and learning a new language brings challenges. The purpose of this research paper is to provide an overview of the Arabic language and the difficulties in learning it.

Key words: ancient language, mother tongue, Semitic language, dialect, globalization, Colloquial Arabic, native speakers.

Аннотация: Изучение арабского языка требует целеустремленности и решимости. Изучение арабского языка может быть трудным, но не забывайте, что каждое новое дело и изучение нового языка сопряжены с трудностями. Целью данной исследовательской работы является предоставление обзора арабского языка и трудностей его изучения.

Ключевые слова: древний язык, родной язык, семитский язык, диалект, глобализация, разговорный арабский язык, носители языка.

Annotatsiya: Arab tilini o'rganish majburiyat va qat'iyatni talab qiladi. Arab tilini o'rganish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin, lekin unutmangki, har bir yangi narsa va yangi tilni o'rganish qiyinchiliklarga olib keladi. Ushbu tadqiqot ishining maqsadi arab tili va uni o'rganishdagi qiyinchiliklar haqida umumiy ma'lumot berishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: qadimgi til, ona tili, semit tili, dialekt, globallashuv, so'zlashuv arab tili, ona tili.

Arabic is one of the most ancient languages, it is an ancient language that existed at least 1500 years ago it is an ancient language that has influenced the whole world. Arabic is the mother tongue of over 300 million people in many countries

including Algeria, Egypt, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates and Yemen. It is the language of the Holy Qur'an, the main book of Islam, and many Muslims around the world are learning Arabic to read the Qur'an in its original language. Arabic is one of the Semitic language families that originated in the northwestern part of the Arabian Peninsula. No one knows when it started, but it is known to date back to the 8th century BC. The language underwent many changes over the years, most of which occurred between the 3rd and 6th centuries AD.

What makes Arabic difficult to learn is that it is a root language, which means that one word can help you find many words. And if you think about it, it doesn't make learning harder, it's actually easier. If you remember the root of the word, you can identify the word you want to remember. Arabic was spoken by nomadic tribes on the northwestern border of the peninsula. It is said that the Arabic word means "nomad". It is the most widely spoken Semitic language today.

Arabic is a unique but beautiful language with many dialects to learn. Nowadays, thanks to the internet and globalization, the Arabic language is once again spreading around the world. In addition, more Arabic students are going abroad for scholarships, which will help spread the language more widely. Arabic has letters like "h" and "ʔ" that do not exist in other languages. English has algebra, algorithm, alchemy, coffee, cotton, ghou, lemon and many other Arabic words.

Now people use a language called colloquial language to communicate with each other. Colloquial Arabic called "Ammiyya" is the Arabic that people use in their daily conversations. It varies from one country to another; every country has different dialects from other countries. You might ask: Is colloquialism slang? And the answer is yes, it's slang. Modern Standard Arabic is the official language of instruction in schools. Also, Arabic is used to write formal things like work reports. It is also taught to those who want to learn Arabic.

According to Arabic learners, the hardest part about learning Arabic is its grammar. Arabic grammar is the hardest thing about it. The words have what are called roots and they change depending on the vowels placed on each letter. Furthermore, the word differs based on gender, dual and plural. The gender of the person you are talking to or about plays a major role. Additionally, some may find that learning the concept of the dual is really difficult as it doesn't exist in many languages. Even native speakers find it hard to learn Arabic grammar. But that is not the case when we talk about Arabic dialects. When it comes to the Arabic writing system most of the learners said that it looks hard but actually it's not hard to learn at all. However, you should know that the Arabic letter changes its shape according to its place in the word. And the fact that Arabic is written and read from right to left takes some time to get used to but it's not hard at all.

Another thing to know about Arabic is that Arabs don't use Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) in their daily life. It is only used in newspapers, radio, TV, formal writing, and in schools. But when Arabs communicate with each other, they use what is called colloquial Arabic (Arabic dialects). There are over 25 Arabic dialects, therefore, you should choose which dialect you want to learn. You could start by learning the basics of Modern Standard Arabic then learn the dialect you want. Or just start learning the dialect you chose right away; the decision is yours to make. And don't worry Arabic is not hard to learn as long as you have your own plan and goals to achieve. Just be persistent and don't listen to the ones who want to break you.

Many people say that Arabic is an important language to learn, even though Arabic is considered difficult to learn. Learning the Arabic language allows people to travel anywhere in the world and study abroad in an Arab country, as well as to understand the Islamic world and read the Qur'an. Arabic is one of the top five languages in the world and is increasingly becoming an important language to learn and excel among other candidate languages.

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